

Synthesis, catalytic and antibacterial activity of ruthenium complexes of 2,2'-dithiobis[*N*-(2-hydroxy-naphth-3-yl)benzamides]

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Manuscript received 22 September 2003, revised 18 February 2004, accepted 18 February 2004

Reaction of 2,2'-dithiobis[*N*-(2-hydroxy-naphth-3-yl)benzamides] (**1**) with RuCl₃·3H₂O, followed by addition of secondary ligands (L = triphenylphosphine (PPh₃), 1,10-phenanthroline (Phen), pyridine (Py), 2,4-diaminotoluene (Diam)), yielded five binuclear metal complexes (**1a-e**). All the compounds were characterised through elemental analyses, magnetic measurements and spectroscopy. Coordination was found to be through the carbonyl oxygen of amide and hydroxyl oxygen of naphthol in an octahedral environment. **1a-e** were found to be effective catalysts for the oxidation of benzyl alcohol and cyclohexanol to benzaldehyde and cyclohexanone in the presence of cooxidant NMO. All the synthesized complexes showed antibacterial properties.

The synthesis of heteronucleating ligands and the coordination chemistry of the heteronuclear complexes derived from such ligands have received considerable interest in recent years¹⁻³. The binuclear metal complexes have been found as interesting models for the coordination environment of metallo-biomolecules⁴. These compounds have gained importance in their utility in promoting multi electron redox reactions, homogeneous catalysis, photochemistry and biological properties⁵.

We have recently reported⁶ the synthesis of ruthenium complexes of 2,2'-dithiobis[2-hydroxyphenyl]benzamide. These compounds exhibited promising *in vitro* antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. typhi* and *E.*

coli. In continuation of our work, we report here in ruthenium(II) complexes of 2,2'-dithiobis[*N*-(2-hydroxy-naphth-3-yl)benzamide]. Our goal is to determine the effect of structural and functional modifications on the metal coordination as well as the effect on their antibacterial and catalytic activities.

Results and discussion

2,2'-Dithiobenzoyl chloride was condensed with 3-amino-2-naphthol in the ratio 1 : 3 to give the brown solid (**1**) in 75% yield (Fig. 1). The reaction of RuCl₃·3H₂O with ligand (**1**) in ethanol yielded a green binuclear compound (**1a**). The interaction of (**1a**) with secondary ligands L (L =

Table 1. Analytical, physical and spectroscopic data of the ruthenium benzamides complexes (**1-1e**)

Complex	Yield (%) / (Colour)	M.p. (°C)	Found (Calcd.) (%)				UV(nm) (ε)	¹ H NMR ^a (δ, ppm)	IR ^b (cm ⁻¹)		
			C	H	N	S			νC=O	νC-N	νN-H
1 C ₃₄ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₂ S ₂ ·2H ₂ O	75 (Blue)	165-172	65.4 (65.4)	4.8 (4.5)	5.1 (4.5)	7.5 (10.2)	260.8 (29588)	10.53 (1H, s), 9.71 (1H, s), 8.47 (2H, s), 7.91-7.28	1624	1536	1350
1a [Ru ₂ (1)Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	85 (Green)	>350	43.2 (43.8)	2.8 (3.2)	4.0 (3.0)	6.1 (6.9)	259.2 (28851), 690.4 (1643)	10.17 (2H, s), 7.68-6.51 (20H, m)	1580	1544	1355
1b [Ru ₂ (1)Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₃ (PPh ₃)]	85 (Blue)	>350	53.7 (53.1)	3.8 (3.7)	3.1 (2.4)	4.5 (5.4)	261.6 (59731), 708 (1989)	10.50 (2H, s), 7.74-7.14 (35H, m)	1581	1541	1357
1c [Ru ₂ (1)Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ (Diam) ₂ ·1.5H ₂ O	76 (Green)	>350	46.2 (46.2)	4.1 (4.6)	6.6 (6.8)	4.7 (5.2)	259.2 (50094), 710.4 (2602)	10.50 (2H, s), 7.70-6.50 (35H, m), 2.2 (3H, s), 2.3 (3H, s)	1583	1544	1384
1d [Ru ₂ (1)Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ (Py) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	80 (Green)	>350	48.4 (48.5)	3.2 (3.7)	5.0 (5.1)	6.2 (5.9)	260.8 (48145), 702.4 (2775)	10.30 (2H, s), 8.35-6.96 (30H, m)	1587	1541	1356
1e [Ru ₂ (1)Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ Phen]·2H ₂ O	87 (Green)	>350	49.3 (49.7)	2.9 (3.4)	5.6 (5.1)	6.3 (5.8)	264 (75021), 682.4 (2085)	10.50 (2H, s), 8.45-6.87 (28H, m)	1584	1541	1354

^aSolvent-DMSO, ^bKBr pellets.

PPh₃, Phen, Py, Diam) yielded the binuclear metal complexes (**1b-e**). The ligand (**1**) was found to be a rigid ligand with the hydroxyl and amido groups lying far apart leading to binuclear metal complexes as observed with metal complexes of 2,2'-dithiobis[2-hydroxyphenyl]benzamide⁶. Elemental analyses also confirmed the complexes to be binuclear. The analytical, physical and spectroscopic data for (**1**), (**1a-e**) are reported in Table 1. All the complexes (**1a-e**) were diamagnetic in accord with the low spin configuration for ruthenium(II), t_{2g}^6 .

The OH and NH stretching frequencies in ligand (**1**) merged and appeared as a broad band at 3405 cm⁻¹ in the IR spectrum. The spectrum of **1** showed strong bands at 1624, 1536 and 1350 cm⁻¹, corresponding to amide bands I, II and III respectively. The amide band I consisted mainly of $\nu_{C=O}$, and the amide II and III bands arose from $\nu_{C=N}$, as well as from δ_{N-H} , although these modes are coupled to one another. According to the literature^{2,7}, when an amide group coordinates through the oxygen atom, a decrease in frequency for amide band I occurs, while there is an increase in frequency for amide bands II and III. The carbonyl stretching frequency in the metal complexes (**1a-e**) occurred at lower frequency (1587–1580) compared to (**1**) ($\nu_{C=O}$, 1624). Amide bands II and III appeared at 1541–1544 cm⁻¹ and 1354–1384 cm⁻¹ compared to **1** (1536 and 1350 cm⁻¹). All the characteristic peaks of secondary ligands PPh₃, Phen, Py and Diam were observed as reported elsewhere⁶.

The ¹H NMR spectrum of (**1**) showed peaks at δ 10.53 and 9.71 ppm corresponding to OH of naphthol group indicating that one of the OH is more hydrogen bonded compared to the other one. The peak at δ 8.47 ppm corresponded to N–H group of the amide. The peaks at δ 7.91–7.27 ppm corresponded to aromatic protons of naphthyl and dithiosalicylic moieties (Table 1). The ¹H NMR spectra in DMSO-*d*₆ for (**1a-e**) revealed a singlet in the δ 10.17–10.50 ppm region downfield compared to **1**, which was assigned to the amide protons inferring the coordination of the amide oxygen to the metal. The aromatic protons appeared as a multiplet in the δ 6.50–8.45 ppm range. The absence of hydroxyl protons in the spectra of metal complexes suggested deprotonation of the hydroxyl proton before coordination of oxygen to the metal. For (**1c**), the NH₂ protons were merged with the aromatic protons and appeared at δ 6.7–7.7 ppm.

The UV-visible spectra of (**1**) and its metal complexes (**1a-e**) recorded in DMSO showed an intense broad band in the region 259–264 nm which was assigned to $\pi-\pi^*$ and $n-\pi^*$ transitions from the aromatic rings. The band in the range 682–710 nm in the metal complexes could be due to *d-d* charge transfer.

Biological studies :

The antimicrobial activity of the complexes (**1**) and (**1a-e**) and the positive control CTAB (cetyl ammonium bromide : a chemical possessing antibacterial properties) shown in Table 2 indicates that the complexes were able to inhibit *in vitro* growth of microorganisms, exhibiting MIC values between 10⁻⁴ and 10⁻⁷ mol dm⁻³. Ligand (**1**) and its ruthenium(II) complexes (**1a-e**) yielded clear inhibition zones around the holes when treated against *S. aureus*, *B. Subtilis*, *E. coli* and *K. aerogenes*. When antibacterial activity of the complexes was carried out at 1.6×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, the compounds precipitated out in the medium.

It was observed from the literature⁸ that increase in aromaticity generally increases the antibacterial activity. 2,2'-Dithiobis[*N*-(2-hydroxy-naphth-3-yl)benzamide] (**1**) containing naphthyl derivative showed more toxicity compared to the previously reported ligand 2,2'-dithiobis(2-hydroxyphenyl)benzamide which possess a phenyl derivative at the concentration of 1.6×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³. The compound RuCl₃.3H₂O and the ligands PPh₃, Phen, Diam, Py were also screened for their antibacterial activity and found to be inactive.

For the Gram-positive bacteria *S. aureus* and *B. Subtilis*, (**1**) and (**1a**) was more potent compared to complexes (**1b-e**) which contains secondary ligands such as PPh₃, Diam, Phen and Py. For Gram-positive bacteria, the complexes exhibited an MIC value of $9.1-8.5 \times 10^{-5}$ mol dm⁻³ except for the derivatives (**1**) and (**1a**) which were active at 1.6×10^{-6} and 1.07×10^{-5} μ g/ml. For the Gram-negative bacteria *E. coli* and *K. aerogenes* (**1**) and its metal complexes (**1a-e**) showed comparable antibacterial activity. All the complexes showed similar activity as compared to positive control CTAB. The metal complexes showed antibacterial activity at an MIC value of $1.07 \times 10^{-6}-9.0 \times 10^{-7}$ mol dm⁻³ for Gram-negative bacteria.

Ligand (**1**) and its ruthenium complexes (**1a-e**) were screened for their ability to inhibit the growth of fungi *C. albicans* and *A. niger*. Each compound was assessed at the conc of $1.6 \times 10^{-4} - 8.5 \times 10^{-5}$ mol dm⁻³ and results are given in Table 2. For *C. Albicans*, the ligand and metal complexes were all essentially ineffective at preventing the growth of candida cells. Ligand (**1**) and (**1a**) inhibit the growth of *A. niger* while the other complexes were inactive.

Catalytic studies :

The results for the catalytic oxidation by the ruthenium complexes are given in Table 3. All the synthesized ruthenium complexes were found to catalyze the oxidation of benzyl alcohol to benzaldehyde and cyclohexanol to

Table 2. Antibacterial activity of the complexes (1-1e)

Complex	Concn. (mol dm ⁻³)	Zone of inhibition (mm)				% Cell growth ^a	
		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>K. aerogenes</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
1	1.60 × 10 ⁻⁴	11.0	11.0	10.5	10.5	91 ± 10	56 ± 6
	1.60 × 10 ⁻⁶	8.0	9.0	8.0	7.50		
	1.07 × 10 ⁻⁴	11.0	11.5	11.5	11.5	82 ± 8	54 ± 4
1a	1.07 × 10 ⁻⁵	9.0	8.0	8.0	9.0		
	1.07 × 10 ⁻⁶	–	–	7.0	7.0		
	8.50 × 10 ⁻⁵	8.0	8.0	10.5	11.0	91 ± 10	102 ± 2
1b	8.50 × 10 ⁻⁶	–	–	9.0	8.50		
	8.50 × 10 ⁻⁷	–	–	7.0	7.0		
	9.00 × 10 ⁻⁵	8.0	10.0	11.0	11.0	82 ± 10	83 ± 10
1c	9.00 × 10 ⁻⁶	–	–	9.50	9.0		
	9.00 × 10 ⁻⁷	–	–	8.0	7.0		
	9.10 × 10 ⁻⁵	10.5	9.50	11.0	11.0	94 ± 10	85 ± 2
1d	9.10 × 10 ⁻⁶	–	–	8.0	8.5		
	9.10 × 10 ⁻⁷	–	–	6.0	7.0		
	9.00 × 10 ⁻⁵	8.0	8.0	10.0	10.5	76 ± 6	77 ± 4
CTAB	9.00 × 10 ⁻⁷	–	–	8.0	9.0		
	3.33 × 10 ⁻⁴	12.5	13.0	12.5	10.0		
Control	–	–	–	–	–	100 ± 4	100 ± 8

^a – 'inactive' ^b Cell growth calcd. against control.

cyclohexanone but the yields and turnover were found to vary with different catalysts used as indicated in Table 3. For the oxidation of alcohols to aldehyde or ketone, 65–98% conversion was obtained. For these reactions refluxing was necessary to achieve high percentage yield while at RT the yield observed was poor.

Table 3. Catalytic activities of complexes (1-1e)

Ruthenium complex	No. of moles of complex used	Substrate	Product	Yield ^a	Turnover ^b
1	1.92 × 10 ⁻²	Benzyl alcohol	–	–	–
	4.00 × 10 ⁻²	Cyclohexanol	–	–	–
1a	2.06 × 10 ⁻²	Benzyl alcohol	A	75.92	35.64
	4.00 × 10 ⁻²	Cyclohexanol	K	77.60	36.75
1b	1.79 × 10 ⁻²	Benzyl alcohol	A	64.33	34.80
	4.03 × 10 ⁻²	Cyclohexanol	K	77.60	41.90
1c	1.46 × 10 ⁻²	Benzyl alcohol	A	69.75	46.30
	4.00 × 10 ⁻²	Cyclohexanol	K	93.82	44.50
1d	1.84 × 10 ⁻²	Benzyl alcohol	A	98.38	51.79
	1.91 × 10 ⁻²	Cyclohexanol	K	68.10	67.54
1e	2.16 × 10 ⁻²	Benzyl alcohol	A	75.45	33.84
	1.93 × 10 ⁻²	Cyclohexanol	K	66.97	65.80

^aYield based on substrate. ^bTurnover = no. of moles of product/no. of moles of complex used.

A : Aldehyde, K : Ketone

	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	x
1a	H ₂ O	H ₂ O	H ₂ O	H ₂ O	–
1b	H ₂ O	H ₂ O	PPh ₃	H ₂ O	–
1c	H ₂ O	Diam	Diam	H ₂ O	5
1d	H ₂ O	Py	Py	H ₂ O	2
1e	H ₂ O	H ₂ O			2

Phen =

Fig. 1. Proposed structure of 1-1e.

Experimental

IR spectra (KBr pellets) were recorded on a Mattson 1000 FT IR spectrometer in the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹, ¹H

and ^{13}C NMR spectra (DMSO) were obtained from a Bruker Spectrospin 250 MHz. The melting point of all samples was determined using a Stuart Scientific Electric Melting point apparatus. Magnetic susceptibility of the metal complexes was carried out on a Sherwood Scientific magnetic balance. Carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and sulfur contents were obtained using a LECO 932 CHNS Mattson 1000 spectrophotometer.

All chemicals were purchased from Aldrich or B.D.H. chemicals and were used without purification with the exception of thionyl chloride and triethylamine. 2,2'-Dithiobis[N-(2-hydroxy-naphth-3-yl)benzamide] (**1**) was synthesized according to the reported method⁸.

Synthesis of 2,2'-dithiobis[N-(2-hydroxy-naphth-3-yl)benzamide] (1): A solution of 3-amino-2-naphthol (4.90 g, 3×10^{-2} mole) in anhydrous dioxane (40 ml) was added dropwise to a suspension of 2,2'-dithiobis(benzoyl chloride) (3.50 g, 1×10^{-2} mol) in dioxane (20 ml) at RT. The reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h at 80° and added with stirring into cold distilled water. The brown precipitate was collected and washed with hot methanol. The dried solid was recrystallized from ethylene glycol monomethyl ether to give a brown solid.

Synthesis of complex [Ru₂(2,2'-dithiobis[N-(2-hydroxy-naphth-3-yl)benzamide] Cl₂(H₂O)₄] (1a): 2,2'-Dithiobis[N-(2-hydroxy-naphth-3-yl)benzamide] (**1**) (1.096 g, 1.20×10^{-3} mole) and RuCl₃·3H₂O (0.50 g) in ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed and stirred for 3 h. The mixture was finally concentrated and a green precipitate was obtained on addition of a few drops of diethylether. The product was washed with a mixture of hot ethanol (10 ml) and dimethylformamide (2 ml), which yielded a green solid which was dried *under vacuo*.

Synthesis of complexes (1b-e): A mixture of (**1a**) (1 mole) and secondary ligands such as (PPh₃, Phen, Py, Diam) (2 mole) in ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed and stirred for 3 h. The resulting mixture was concentrated and the compound was obtained on addition of a diethylether. The obtained product was washed with a mixture of hot ethanol (10 ml) and dimethylformamide (2 ml) and dried *under vacuo*.

Antibacterial: The four bacteria used in the screening were *E. coli*, *B. subtilis*, *K. aerogenes* and *S. aureus*. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC, mol dm⁻³) was determined by the dilution method. The MIC was defined as the lowest concentration of drug inhibited the growth of each microorganism.

The agar plates were set accordingly using 18.0 ml of

Mueller-Hinton agar and 2–3 drops of the NaCl mixture. Two holes were punched apart with a loop and the tested solution was put in it. The results were read as the measurement of the inhibition zone, that is, the diameter (in mm) of the zone in which no microorganisms survived. The mean value of the two readings of the diameter was taken. The value included the diameter of the hole made in the agar plate.

Antifungal activity: The antifungal activities were evaluated against *A. niger* and *C. albicans* by the agar plate technique. The compounds were dissolved in 10% DMSO at a conc of 1.6×10^{-4} – 8.5×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³. Duplicates were used in each case. The growth of the fungus was obtained by measuring the diameter of the colony after 48 h. The % cell growth for the control (10% DMSO) was taken as 100% growth and % cell growth for the tests solution were calibrated against the control.

Catalytic studies: To the solution of the benzyl alcohol (0.1 ml) in dichloromethane (10 ml), NMO (3 mmol) and the complex (2×10^{-2} mmol) was added. The mixture was refluxed for 3 h under vigorous stirring conditions in the presence of 4 Å molecular sieves. The solvent was evaporated and ether (5 × 5 ml) was used to extract the benzaldehyde. The combined ethereal mixture was filtered and finally quantified as dinitrophenylhydrazone.

To a solution of the cyclohexanol (0.2 ml) in dichloromethane (15 ml), NMO (6 mmol) and the metal complex (4×10^{-2} mmol) was added. The mixture was refluxed for 3 h under vigorous stirring conditions. The reaction mixture was then concentrated and the cyclohexanone was separated by column chromatography (packed with silica gel) using hexane and ethyl acetate (3 : 2) as the eluent. The weight of the resulting ketone was then recorded.

Acknowledgement

We thank the University of Mauritius for financial support.

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